

RESEARCH PROPOSAL

Employability Skills for the Key Positions: Bangladeshi RMG Sector Context

This proposal is submitted
as a part of regular and internal research activities of
Bangladesh Institute of Management (BIM)

RESEARCH GROUP

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Dhaka, 29 November 2022

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1.0 BACKGROUND AND CONTEXT

Readymade garments (RMG) sector being a major part of Bangladeshi industries, have been playing a very crucial and critical role on economic development (Mia and Akter, 2019). In its historical journey, RMG sector has been continuously increasing the export volume (Farhana et al., 2022), (Islam, 2021), and more significantly, generating employment for the wide range of people (Islam, 2021), (Islam et al., 2016). The RMG sector is directly impacting on the gross domestic product (GDP), through wide range of employment rather than export earnings (Uddin, 2014).

Though generating huge employment, unfortunately, from this vital sector, huge foreign currency has been remitting to the other countries through employments (Tuhin, 2022), (Noor, 2018). They are employed in key positions in RMG and textile sectors in the mid-level key positions (TextileToday, 2017) and being paid almost 20% extra salary (Noor, 2018) which resulting annually \$2 billion remittance to our neighbouring countries (Fazal and Ahmed, 2020). Hence, the country facing deficiency of foreign currency reserve in spite of high export.

2.0 INTRODUCTION

The huge number of foreign nationals employed in the RMG sector in Bangladesh (Tuhin, 2022) has triggered the study. Therefore, study aims to figure out the skills required to perform the key positions in the RMG sector in Bangladesh, because if the Bangladeshi nationals would apprehend these skills, the foreign employment would be reduced.

Skills deficiencies in RMG sector are a very common problem in Bangladesh (Sarker et al., 2019). Particularly, lack in managerial skills and communications skills found as a barrier of employment of the native people (Wali, 2021).

Bangladeshi researchers on many occasions have argued for adequate expertise to work successfully in the RMG sector (Hossian et al., 2019), (Zaman et al., 2018). As stated earlier, we have lacking in this area and the foreign people are exploring this opportunity, which results in huge foreign currency remittance from Bangladesh.

Bangladesh is a highly populated country (Farid and Mostari, 2022), (Karim et al., 2022) with an estimated total population of 16.50 crore (Bangladesh Bureau of Statistics). Beside the burden of this huge population, the crucial challenge is employment (Mamun et al., 2020), (Siddiqui, 2019). This situation became worse as the graduates hold negative attitudes toward social entrepreneurship (Tu et al., 2021), but it could be a good solution for unemployment. As stated earlier, foreign nationals are taking such opportunities and exploring the gap in the RMG sector in Bangladesh.

This study is neither involved in reducing the foreign remittance nor arranging employment for the Bangladeshi people. It deals with identifying the required skills for the key positions in the RMG sector.

2.1 Objective of the Study

The study deals with a couple of objectives related to the employability skills required for the RMG sector in Bangladesh.

- To classify the key positions where the foreign nationals are working in the RMG sector in Bangladesh.
- To identify the skills required for successfully perform the key positions in Bangladeshi RMG Sector.

2.2 Scope of the Study

The study is limited within the readymade garments, apparels and textile sectors. Furthermore, it focuses on the skills for the key positions.

3.0 RATIONALE OF THE STUDY

It has been established that Bangladeshi nationals are not working in the key positions in the RMG sector and as result foreigners are working and earning billions of US Dollar every year. A recent study from the Transparency International Bangladesh (TIB) has revealed that \$3.15 billion are being remitted out of Bangladesh every year (Manzoor-E-Khoda, 2020). Not only that, TIB also mentions that this amount is often transferred illegally, as the many of the foreign workers work here on tourist visa and interestingly the employers are arranging such employment (Manzoor-E-Khoda, 2020).

TIB has also figured out the percentage of different foreign nationals working in Bangladesh as presented bellow:

Major country-wise distribution of foreign nationals working in Bangladesh

Sources: (Fazal and Ahmed, 2020), TIB.

In addition, it has been reported that the RMG sector has been unsuccessful in appealing the graduates from the best universities in Bangladesh. A survey has noticed that 68% graduates are unwilling to pursue their career in RMG sector (Fazal and Ahmed, 2020).

Altogether, it is critically essential to figure out the skills required for the key positions in the RMG sector, as well as to change the motivation of the fresh graduates. However, in this dilemma, the study is focusing only identification of the required skills.

4.0 PROPOSED METHODOLOGY

The skills required in the key positions in RMG sector in Bangladesh are identifiable through qualitative research, because the study belongs to social constructivism paradigm which refers to usual qualitative research approach (Creswell, 2014).

The scholars and researchers from of different times across the world (Morgan and Krueger, 1993), (Morgan and Krueger, 1998), (Greenbaum, 1998), (Bloor, 2001), (Gill et al., 2008), (Stewart and Shamdasani, 2014), (Rosenthal, 2016), (O. Nyumba et al., 2018) have emphasized on focus group discussions for qualitative research with numerous benefits; flexibilities in selecting of suitable participants, innovation managers in this case, allowing the participants to be open in discussions, managing the insights and thoughts of the participants in accordance with the research objectives etc.

Therefore, the study is proposing to conduct the research through focus group discussion as a qualitative research method.

4.1 Research Approach

Research approaches include plans and processes that narrow-down wide assumptions into specific method for collecting, analysing and interpreting data (Creswell, 2014) and selection of research approaches totally related and reliant on the nature of research problems.

The current research, aims to identify the skills required for the key position in the RMG sector, it proposes to deploy focus group discussion as a qualitative research method.

4.2 Sampling

The study proposes qualitative research where focus group discussion is the research method. There are around 4,000 readymade garments in Bangladesh (BIDA, 2022). Participants for focus group discussions will be randomly selected as referred to the simple sampling technique (Cochran, 2007). Apart from this it ensures that participation of at least giant RMG factories support the sampling effectively (Sharma, 2017).

The ideal number of a focus group ranges from 6 to 8 (Robinson, 2020), (Krueger et al., 2000) which can be extended up to 12 (Khan et al., 1991).

4.3 Study Location

The study covers the all the readymade garments in Bangladesh.

4.4 Respondent Groups

The divisional heads of human resource, or at least the human resource managers are the respondents for the study who will participate in the focus group discussion.

4.5 Data Collection Tool and Analysis Plan

The study will collect information through focus group discussion. The qualitative data, derived from the FG discussion, will be analysed qualitatively.

5.0 STUDY PLAN/ACTIVITY SCHEDULE

The entire study is divided into several tasks, such as literature review, research design, research execution, analyses of findings, and report writing. The time frame for the tasks is presented bellow:

		WEEKS											
Serial	Activities	W-01	W-02	W-03	W-04	W-05	W-06	W-07	W-08	W-09	W-10	W-11	W-12
01	Literature Review	■	■	■								■	■
02	Research Design				■	■							
03	Research Execution						■	■	■	■			
04	Analyses of Findings									■	■		
05	Report Writing											■	■

6.0 CONTRIBUTION OF THE STUDY

The study is very crucial as it will explore the required skills for successfully perform the key positions, occupied by the foreign nationals, in the Bangladeshi RMG sector. It will provide the scenario of foreign employment. In further research, this study will contribute to develop our native people to be employed in those key positions; which will reduce unemployment and foreign remittance out of the country.

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APPENDICES

A.1 Study Expenditure

The total expenditure of the study mainly involves the honorarium of the researchers. A small portion is required for research execution and miscellaneous purposes. The breakdown of total expenditure is given below:

Serial		Rate	Person	Total
01	Studying Literature – as research honorarium	20,000.00	3.00	60,000.00
02	Designing the Research – as research honorarium	30,000.00	3.00	90,000.00
03	Executing the Research – as research honorarium	10,000.00	3.00	30,000.00
04	Analyzing the Findings – as research honorarium	30,000.00	3.00	90,000.00
05	Writing the Report – as research honorarium	35,000.00	2.00	70,000.00
06	Miscellaneous	25,000.00		25,000.00
TOTAL EXPENDITURE				365,000.00
(In Words) Taka Three Lac Sixty Five Thousand only				

A.2 Researchers' Profile

Mohammad Nazmi Newaz

Mohammad Nazmi Newaz has a solid academic orientation with BBA and MBA from the University of Dhaka, Bangladesh and a Master of Laws from the Queensland University of Technology, Australia. He is a seasoned academic and researcher with a demonstrated history of teaching and research in management, innovation and entrepreneurship development. He is highly equipped with the knowledge of innovation, entrepreneurship, management, business development, team building, and HR management. He is a 19 years' recognized academic and research professional with a Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) focused in organizational innovativeness for service delivery in the water utilities from the University of Newcastle, Australia.

Momotaz Khatun

Momotaz Khatun has a firm academic orientation with BBA and MBA in Management and Human Resource Management consecutively from the University of Dhaka, Bangladesh. Now she is working as Associate Management Counsellor at Bangladesh Institute of Management (BIM). BIM which is a renowned training institute in Bangladesh. She is interested in the field of Management, Human Resource Management, Total Quality Management, Entrepreneurship and business development.

Md. Nazmus Sakib

Md. Nazmus Sakib is an Associate Management Counsellor Bangladesh Institute of Management, 4, Sobhanbag, Mirpur road, Dhaka – 1207, Bangladesh. He completed B.Sc. Engineering on Building Engineering & Construction Management from Khulna University of Engineering & Technology (KUET). He has served 3.5 year as a Junior individual consultant under Dhaka WASA at Dasherbandi Sewage Treatment Plant (500 MLD). He is interested in the field of Operations Management, Quality Management and Sustainable Manufacturing.